

Hybrid GAN and Fourier Transformation for SAR Ocean Pattern Image Augmentation*

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Abstract—Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) image generation using Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) has attracted significant attention in recent years. In addition, the ocean plays a crucial role in regulating Earth’s climate system. SAR images provide valuable information for ocean observation and analysis, aiding the understanding of oceanic processes and their role in climate change. This study presents a GAN-based approach for generating realistic and diverse ocean-pattern SAR images. The proposed methodology combines a style-based generator network with an adversarial discriminator network to learn and reproduce complex and unique patterns present in SAR images. To avoid discriminator overfitting, which frequently occurs because of insufficient training data, an adaptive discriminator augmentation (ADA) mechanism has been exploited. By training GAN with ADA, the generator learns to capture the spatial and statistical properties of oceanic phenomena in restricted data regimes. However, the generated images were not fruitful in terms of their physical properties. By examining the Fourier spectrum of the generated images, we found a lack of meaningful spectrum and variety in the frequency domain. To address this issue and improve the frequency spectrum of the generated images, we modified the loss functions of the network by adding the mean square error of the generated images and real images in the frequency domain.

Index Terms—Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), ocean SAR image generation, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), Fourier transformation, and data augmentation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Artificial Intelligence methods ask for large training and benchmark data sets. Thanks to the development of remote sensing (RS) satellite technology, the resolution of images is constantly improved, increasing the observed details. This poses major challenges to obtaining labeled data sets mainly for Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images. One of

the main directions to address the problem that only limited labeled SAR image data are available is to implement the data augmentation method based on Deep Learning (DL). In this study, we exploit a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) for SAR image generation.

GANs require adversarially training a generator and discriminator network so that the generator learns to duplicate the desired data distribution. Despite recent gains in random image generation tasks [1] [2], we can identify GAN-generated images from real images in the frequency domain, indicating that existing GANs fail to learn the spectral distributions. According to recent research [3] [4], the frequency spectrum difference arises primarily at high frequencies. Because high-frequency picture components influence the exactness of features, the discrepancy cannot be ignored for generative tasks where details are important. Standard GAN may fail to generate the desired data distribution when real data contains considerably high frequencies. Furthermore, since the Fourier transform is a bijective mapping, the frequency spectrum discrepancy between real data and the generated samples also indicates that the data distribution in image space is not well captured. We believe that reducing the spectrum discrepancy will boost the performance of GANs.

The ocean plays a crucial role in regulating Earth’s climate system, and by observing it, we can gain insights into the complex interactions between the ocean, atmosphere, and other climate components. SAR plays a pivotal role in advancing our understanding of the world’s oceans. One of its most significant advantages in oceanography is its all-weather capability. Unlike optical sensors, which are hindered by cloud cover and darkness, SAR can operate effectively regardless of weather conditions, providing a continuous stream of data crucial for studying dynamic ocean processes.

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Furthermore, SAR is instrumental in maritime applications, including ship detection [5] [6] [7] and oil spill [8] [9] monitoring. Its capacity to detect vessels and oil slicks on the ocean surface aids in maritime surveillance and environmental protection efforts. Coastal regions also benefit from SAR’s monitoring capabilities, as it assists in tracking coastal erosion [10] [11] [12], sea-level rise [13] [14], and changes in coastal habitats. Whether it’s assessing the health of marine ecosystems, managing fisheries, or responding to environmental emergencies, SAR is instrumental in tracking the extent and movement of sea ice in polar regions [15] [16], contributing to climate research and navigation safety.

To the best of our knowledge, the majority of SAR image augmentation research uses the MSTAR dataset and concentrates on data augmentation for SAR image target detection or recognition [17] [18] [19] but not ocean pattern image generation. We exploit ocean SAR vignettes from Sentinel-1 wave mode for training the GAN, in order to generate unobserved ocean pattern images in categories of different oceanic or atmospheric phenomena. Using well-generated ocean patterns, we can predict oceanic phenomena. The methodology is discussed in the next section. Section 3 presents the experimental results, while Section 4 draws conclusions.

II. METHODOLOGY

The paper presents the methodology of StyleGAN with ADA [20], an extension of the original StyleGAN [21] framework with dynamic discriminator augmentation during training. The core architecture of StyleGAN, consisting of a style-based generator and progressive growing, remains unchanged in ADA. The discriminator augmentation strategy involves applying random augmentations to both real and generated images, enhancing its robustness and generalization capability. Various image transformations like rotation, translation, scaling, color transformations, and occlusion can be used for augmentation, and the augmentation strength is adaptively controlled based on the discriminator’s recent performance. The discriminator and generator are trained with binary cross-entropy loss in an adversarial manner, where the generator’s objective is to deceive the discriminator and produce realistic images.

The training process involves iteratively updating the generator and discriminator networks. The generator aims to minimize the discriminator’s ability to distinguish between real and generated images, while the discriminator aims to accurately classify them. The adaptive augmentation strategy ensures a balanced training process and prevents the discriminator from dominating the training. Further implementation details, optimization algorithms, and hyperparameter tuning are covered in the subsequent section.

In order to increase the frequency spectrum discrepancy, we modify the loss function with an additional term. In the standard GANs, the adversarial loss for the discriminator is defined as:

$$L_D = -\mathbb{E}_{x \sim P_{data}(x)}[\log D(x)] \quad (1)$$

$$-\mathbb{E}_{x \sim P_g(x)}[\log(1 - D(x))],$$

where $D(x)$ represents the probability of x comes from P_{data} rather than the generator’s distribution P_g . In other words, $D(x)$ measures the quality of the generated sample of x . However, only this criterion usually fails to generate samples that are realistic in the frequency domain. Therefore, we calculate the Fourier transform of the generated image, \hat{x} and x . For a discrete two-dimensional signal $f(m, n)$ representing an image of size MN , we first compute the discrete Fourier transform F of it,

$$F(k, l) = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} f(m, n) e^{-2\pi i \frac{km}{M}} e^{-2\pi i \frac{ln}{N}}, \quad (2)$$

where $k = 0, \dots, M - 1$ and $l = 0, \dots, N - 1$ are the spectral coordinates. Then we calculate the spectrum of an image as:

$$r = \sqrt{k^2 + l^2}. \quad (3)$$

We define a Mean Square Error (MSE) to calculate the discrepancy between generated images and real images in the frequency domain. The MSE of the spectrum of generated image (\hat{r}) and the spectrum of real image (r) is defined as:

$$MSE(r, \hat{r}) = \frac{1}{MN} \sum_{j=0}^{MN} (r_j - \hat{r}_j). \quad (4)$$

Finally, the adversarial loss is a combination of L_D and $MSE(r, \hat{r})$ with the importance weight for the MSE of a spectrum which is defined as:

$$L_{adv} = L_D + \lambda MSE(r, \hat{r}), \quad (5)$$

where λ is a hyperparameter that controls the relative importance of spatial and spectral losses.

Fig. 1: An example of each class of TenGeoP-SARwv [?].

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Dataset

The dataset TenGeoP-SARwv, as provided by [22], comprises 37,560 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) images sourced from Sentinel-1A WV acquisitions. These images represent ten distinct atmospheric and ocean-related physical phenomena. Sentinel-1 WV vignettes are obtained by alternating center incidence angles, specifically 23.8° (WV1) and 36.8° (WV2), every 100 km along the satellite’s flight path. Each vignette exhibits a spatial resolution of 5 meters and covers a footprint of 20 x 20 km. This dataset primarily focuses on SAR vignettes polarized with VV (default polarization).

Fig. 2: an example of four subclasses with different orientations and the Fourier spectrum of 12 samples for each subclass.

Figure 3 shows the spectrum of real images and generated images (randomly chosen) when $\lambda = 0, 1, 10^2, 10^5, 10^7$, respectively.

The provided images are derived from Sentinel-1 WV data processed through Single Look Complex (SLC) processing. Two versions of these images are available: PNG and GeoTIFF. In the PNG version, pixel values are normalized into an 8-bit grayscale range ($[0, 255]$), while in the GeoTIFF version, pixel values are normalized on a 16-bit scale ($[0, 65,535]$). Despite the higher precision of GeoTIFF files, PNGs are more suitable for visual interpretation and are compatible with the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models employed in this study. To prepare the PNG images for CNN processing, they were pre-processed to have values within the range of $-1, +1$, given their 8-bit grayscale nature. Additionally, considering the varied sizes of the original images (typically around 500^2), they were resized to a consistent size of 256^2 pixels. This resizing was essential to ensure that the images met the required input dimensions for the CNN models used in the experiments. The ten distinct classes referred to in [22] are illustrated in Figure 1 along with their corresponding class names.

B. Qualitative Evaluation

The final results of the proposed method are presented in this section. The model was trained independently on each ocean pattern class separately. Figure 2 depicts 6 randomly generated images for each class in order. The generated images are in PNG format (uint8) and have the same resolution as the original images (256^2). While the training data is

limited, StyleGAN with ADA uses augmentation approaches to generate high-quality images with great diversity.

As can be seen in Figure 1, some classes such as pure ocean waves have homogeneous intensity modulation and periodic signatures of ocean waves. In contrast, sea ice consists of complex textural contexts and has significant intensity contrasts between different patches [22]. Therefore, the behavior of the model to train such different oceanic phenomena can be discussed.

However, the Fourier spectrum of generated images is not realistic. That means the network can not preserve the physical properties of the SAR images. In order to assess the behavior of the model in terms of the physical properties of the data, we look at the generated images of the Pure Ocean wave class more closely. In general, we categorize the samples of this class into four subclasses regarding the orientation of the wave. Figure 2 shows an example of four subclasses with different orientations and the Fourier spectrum of 12 samples for each subclass. As can be seen, the Fourier spectrum provides information regarding the velocity and direction of the wave. Therefore, we compare the generated images with real images in the frequency domain using the Fourier spectrum of both real and generated images.

We can see the spectrum of real images in the first column is sharp so that we can estimate the direction and velocity of the waves. However, the spectrums of generated images (other columns) are smooth and not similar to the first column's spectrums. In addition, by looking at the second column we realize that the variety of generated images in the frequency domain is low because most of the spectrums are in one

Fig. 3: The spectrum of real images and generated images (randomly chosen) when $\lambda = 0, 1, 10^2, 10^5, 10^7$, respectively.

direction. By increasing λ , the importance of the Fourier loss term, we witness more variants and sharper spectrums. However, the last column corresponds to $\lambda = 10^7$ and shows spectrums with artifacts and chessboard patterns in all samples. As a result, $\lambda = 10^5$ might be an optimal value since the model generates images with sharper and more variant spectrums which is more similar to the spectrum of generated images than different values of λ .

C. Quantitative Evaluation

In order to quantitatively compare real and generated images regarding these two properties, we calculate the Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) which captures the similarity of generated images to real ones better than the Inception Score. The results are provided by FIDs using 50,000 images drawn randomly from the training set, and report the lowest distance encountered over the course of training. It is worth noting that a lower value of FID demonstrates better performance. We consider the Ocean Pure Wave and Sea Ice categories to evaluate the importance of the Fourier spectrum loss term.

FID values regarding the model without Fourier spectrum ($\lambda = 0$) and when $\lambda = 1, 10^2, 10^5, 10^7$ as a function of the training progress (the number of images shown to D) are shown in Figure 4. As can be seen, FID for pure ocean waves

cannot provide a considerable decrease after a few steps. In other words, the model learns fast the simple features and training is not fruitful anymore. However, $\lambda = 1$ converges faster than others and $\lambda = 10^2$ has the lowest FID at the end. In order to assess the importance of the Fourier loss term, we analyze the FID values for Sea Ice samples. The right chart in Figure 4 shows the FID convergence for Sea Ice. In this chart, $\lambda = 1$ and $\lambda = 10^2$ provide better performance due to the lower FID compared to the others. The interesting result is related to $\lambda = 10^7$ which shows a big fluctuation after some steps and leads to divergence.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this research, we harnessed the power of StyleGAN alongside adaptive discriminator augmentation to generate SAR ocean pattern images. Our approach addresses the common challenge of limited labeled data by leveraging the benefits of augmentation strategies. Despite encountering the hurdle of a training dataset size below 5,000 instances—typically deemed inadequate for effective GAN training and prone to issues such as overfitting and generator divergence—our results demonstrated the model’s impressive capability to produce high-quality images. Significantly, this success was achieved while ensuring that the augmentation distribution did not compromise the authenticity of the generated data.

However, an observation emerged from our analysis—generated images in the frequency domain did not closely resemble real images. Our investigation into the Fourier spectrum revealed distinct differences between real and generated images, making the latter easily detectable. In response to this limitation, we took a proactive step to enhance the model’s ability to preserve physical properties. To achieve this, we introduced a modification to the loss function, incorporating an additional term that computes the MSE between real and generated images in the frequency domain. The subsequent evaluation of the significance of this additional loss term involved a comprehensive exploration, both qualitatively and quantitatively, by systematically increasing the weighting parameter (λ). This research contributes valuable insights into refining GAN-based image generation methods, emphasizing the importance of incorporating domain-specific considerations to improve the fidelity of generated content.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 860370.

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Fig. 4: FID convergence versus the number of images (multiple by 100) shown to Discriminator. Pure Ocean Waves is represented on the left and Sea Ice on the right.

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